
**AWARENESS AND USE OF OPEN ACCESS E-RESOURCES BY THE
FACULTY MEMBERS OF KARMAVEER BHURAO PATIL
POLYTECHNIC, SATARA: A STUDY**

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to determine the level of awareness of open access electronic resources by the faculty members of Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil (KBP) Polytechnic, Satara. The study mainly focused on the use of different types of Open Access Electronic Resources (E-Resources) by the faculty, Source of Awareness, Learn to use, problems faced, purpose of use, preferred search engines and search methods for effective retrieval of E- Information Resources. For this purpose the researchers prepared a well-structured web based questionnaire as a tool for data collection. The collected questionnaire has been analyzed and presented with useful percentage analysis and suitable tables and graphs for presentation of data. The article concluded with summaries of the results highlighting the Major Findings and Qualitative Suggestions.

Key Words: *E-Resources, Open Access, Awareness of e-resources, use of e-resources.*

Introduction:

In any educational institution, libraries play a colossal role that cannot be dispensed with. They act as the hub of learning resources and activities both for teachers and students. It is the springboard and the destination that the core of learning takes place. The modern day paves the way for its users to use the libraries at their utmost and fullest satisfaction. The bottom-line is libraries save their users' time hugely. The credit goes to technology. In this age of globalization, ICTs facilitate quick and easy access to a wide range of information/information resources worldwide. In fact, it is now difficult to imagine a world without information technology. The provision and use of ICT

is part and parcel of the entire system, to both the students, Faculty members and the institutions. Libraries with the help of computerized media data keep the world alert, dynamic and sophisticated. The modern day advents such as E- books, E-journals, E-conferences, known as e resources, save people's time and money in many ways. Many of us always search the resources through Google search engine with a thought that Google will provide us with the most relevant and authoritative resources, which is not always true. There are various categories of e-resources like subscribed e-resources and open access e resources or consortium e-resources. The information is more now, what kind of information people are accessing are these reliable questions. So

here come open-access resources which are freely available on the internet and these resources are very much authentic and reliable. In India, many institutions are providing open access e resources. The purpose of this study is to identify how open access electronic information resources are utilized by Faculty members in KBP Polytechnic.

Meaning and Definition:

The concept of 'Openness' is based on the idea that knowledge should be disseminated and shared freely through the Internet for the benefit of society as a whole. The two most important aspects of open access are free availability and as few restrictions as possible on the use of the resources, whether technical, legal or price barriers. (Yuan et al.,2008). (Suber, 2011) defines Open Access Resources as "Digital, online, free of charge, and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions". Public Library of Science (PLoS) defines it as "free availability and unrestricted use".(Suber, 2015).However, (Jain, 2012) defines open access materials as full text, can be accessed by anybody from anywhere and its contents can be in any format from texts and data to software, audio, video, and multimedia, scholarly articles and their preprints. Open access literature can be applied to all forms of published research output, including scholarly journal articles, conference papers, theses, book chapters and monographs (Schöpfel, 2013; Meredith, 2012).

Literature Review:

According to BOAI (Budapest Open Access Initiative, 2002), Open means free for readers, not for publishers. Open access literatures aren't free to produce. But that doesn't close the door

for readers to get it free of charge.(Suber, 2015) stated that none of the OA advocates said Open Access literature has no publication cost, though a number of them claimed that the cost to produce open access literature is less expensive than the traditionally published one. Open Educational Resources Open education can be seen as an umbrella covering a number of concepts such as Open Educational Resources, open source, open access, open science, open archiving and open publishing. (Peters, 2008), (Peter & Deimann, 2013). The idea of Open Educational Resources (OERs) was mentioned for the first time in 2002 at the UNESCO Forum on Open Courseware for Higher Education. (Butcher, 2011), (Poposki, 2010).The key purpose of OER is to provide free access to high-quality educational resources on a large scale. Resources of Open Education are in three areas- learning content, tools and implementation resources. (Yuan, 2008).

About KBP Polytechnic, Satara:

Rayat Shikshan Sanstha's Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Polytechnic, Satara is one of the prestigious educational institutions in the state of Maharashtra. This Institute was established in Year 1983 and has continued its esteemed journey for the last 35 Years, and it is Affiliated to Maharashtra State Board Of Technical Education, Mumbai and approved by AICTE, New Delhi & DTE Maharashtra. Provide Excellent Academic, Physical, Administrative, infrastructural and Moral ambience. Promote quality and excellence in teaching learning.

Methodology:

The study was limited to the Faculty Members of Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Polytechnic, Satara. A online

questionnaire survey was conducted to collect the information regarding the use of e-resources, frequency of use of e-resources, purpose of using e-resources, frequency of locating desired information, problems faced by the users while using e-resources. A total of 51 questionnaires were distributed to collect the primary data out of which 45 questionnaires were found usable for analysis. The collected data was analyzed and presented in the tabular and graphical form.

Objectives:

An objective of the present study is to;

- Analyze the awareness and utilization of open access e- resources
- Determine the level of awareness of open access electronic e- resources by Faculty Members of KBP Polytechnic
- Identify the purpose of the use of open access e-resources by Faculty members
- Find out the frequency of online resources used by Faculty members
- Identify the difficulties encountered by the users while accessing open access e - resources.
- Suggest improvement measures based on the findings of the study.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

1. Gender wise respondent's distribution:

Sr. No.	Gender	Response
1	Male	16 (36%)
2	Female	29 (64%)
Total		45 (100%)

(Source: - Primary Data)

Above Pie chart shows the gender wise distribution of the respondents. It shows that 64% of the participants were female and 36% of the participants were male.

2. Awareness of Open Access E-Resource:

Sr. No.	Gender	Response
1	Yes- Aware	43 (96%)
2	No- Not Aware	2 (4%)

(Source: - Primary Data)

Above Pie chart shows that most (96%) of the Faculty members are aware of open access e-resources. However, 4% of the Faculty members are unaware about the open access e-resources available on Internet.

3. Place of Accessing Open Access E-Resources:

(Source: - Primary Data)

The Open access e-resources can be used in different places according to the convenience of the user and availability Internet access. Above bar chart shows that majority 55.60% of the respondents access e-resources at remotely like their Home, Net cafe etc., 53.30% faculty members access information resources at college library, 51.10% access at Computer Lab, and 42.20% faculties accessed in campus.

4. Frequency of using Open Access E-Resources:

(Source: - Primary Data)

Above Pie chart shows that majority 40% respondent used open access e-resources weekly, 27 % respondents used open access e-resources twice in a week, 15% of

the respondents used Open Access e-resources daily. Followed, 18% respondents used once in a month.

5. The Purpose of Using Open Access E- –Resources:

Sr. No	Purposes of use	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	For studying course work	31	68.9%
2	For updating subject knowledge	33	73.3%
3	For teaching	37	82.2%
4	For writing research papers	8	17.8%
5	To get information for Academic, Research and Project work/Assignments	21	46.7%
6	For Higher education/ further development in the field	11	24.4%
7	Any other	2	4.4%

(Source: - Primary Data)

The data presented in the above table indicated that the purpose of using open access e-resources by Faculty Members. The study revealed that the majority of Faculty Members 82.2% used Open access for Teaching., whereas 73.7% respondents used open access for updating subject knowledge, followed by

68.9% respondents used open access resources to for course work, 46.7% respondents used open access e-resources for other academic activities, Research wok and project work / Assignments The study revealed that majority of the Faculty members used open access e-resources for teaching.

6. Usage of various types of Open Access scholarly Resources:

Sr. No.	Types of open access e resources	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	E-Journal Articles	25	55.6%
2	E-Books	33	73.3%
3	E-Newspaper	35	77.8%
4	Electronic/Online Databases	16	35.6%
5	E-Patent	04	8.9%
6	E-Thesis & Dissertation	05	11.1%
7	E-Reports	06	13.3%
8	Miscellaneous (Editorials, etc.)	2	4.4%

(Source: - Primary Data)

Table shows the use of Open Access electronic e-resources among faculty members. It is evident that the majority of the faculty members 77.8% used Open Access E -Newspaper. The study revealed that the 73.3% Faculty Members used Open Access E-books. Comparatively less percentage of faculty members used 55.6% open Access E-Journals. Followed by 35.6% used Electronic/Online Databases, 13.3% E-Reports, 11.1% E-Thesis & Dissertation, 44.32% E-newspapers, it also found that 8.9% of faculty members rarely used E-Patent.

7. Advantages of Using Open Access E – Resources:

(Source: - Primary Data)

From the above Table shows the responses of faculties about advantages for

9. Problems encountered while Accessing E-Resources:

Sr. No.	Purpose	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	Finding mass irrelevant information	16	35.6%
2	Time consuming	8	17.8%
3	Slow access speed	18	40%
4	Lack of Searching knowledge	10	22.2%
5	Lack of Library staff assistance	06	13.3%
6	Difficulty in searching required information	09	20%
7	Required subscribed contents	15	33.3%
8	NA	2	4.4%

(Source: - Primary Data)

using open access e-resources 53.30% of respondents about reasons for using e-resources for ease of access followed by 51.10% respondents used open access e-resources time saving, 48.90% respondents used open access e-resources because it is more informative and 37.80% respondents used open access e-resources more effective.

8. Level of satisfaction with Open Access E-Resources:

(Source: - Primary Data)

A question was asked to know the level of satisfaction of the open access e-resources. It is observed from the above Pie chart that majority 71 % of the respondents stated that they are satisfied with open access e-resources, while 27 % faculties highly satisfied, 2 % averagely satisfied.

There are many problems reported while using e-resources. Above Table reveals 40% reported lack of slow access internet speed, 35.6% face difficulty in finding irrelevant information from the open access e-resources, 33.3 % reported required subscribed contents, and 22.2 % faculties have no knowledge for searching. 20% reported Difficulty in searching required information.

Findings:

The major findings of the study indicate that majority of the respondents are aware of the open access e- resources (such as E-Books, E-Journals E-Newspaper, Electronic/Online Databases, E-Patent, E-Thesis & Dissertation, E-Reports). Large numbers of faculty members are using these open Access e-resources for their academic related work like writing research papers, for teaching etc. Most of the faculty members strongly agreed with the necessity for computer and Internet literacy to access the electronic information resources.

Conclusion:

In the changing information environment in electronic era the users have knowledge about availability if e-resources in KBP Polytechnic library. Many users also need to know the complete potential of the open access resources. The library should provide and explore more facilities about the open access resources those are freely available on Internet. Accordingly, the library has to evolve more scientific methods to develop and organize open a standard open access collection of E-resources. It is concluded that open access e-resources which are available through library website are being effectively used by the KBP users. It is

recommended that the management of the Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Polytechnic Library should provide functional Internet facilities for the Faculties, library organize regular workshops and seminars aimed at informing their Faculties on the relevance and use of open access electronic e-resources

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the study the following suggestions

1. Library should start Open e-resources center for the library users.
2. Library should organize practical sessions, workshops on effective use of open e- resources for their users
3. The library should arrange various user awareness programs /orientation and training programs for proper utilization of open access e-resources to achieve their educational goals.
4. Well-equipped digital library facility should be provided to the library users by the institute. Faculty should guide and make them acquainted with the use of electronic resources for their academic and, curricular activities.
5. Library should facilitate Strong Internet connection speed for instant and bulky data at a time.
6. Wide publicity of open access resources are required, more facility (computers and high speed internet) in campus required.
7. Library should make a marketing of their web portal among the users.

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